

Finite Element Analysis of Composite Frames in Wheelchair under Upward Loading

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Abstract : The finite element analysis is adopted in this primary study. Using the Tsai-Wu criterion and delamination criterion, the stacking sequence $[45/0_4/-45_4/90_4]_s$ is the final optimal design for the wheelchair frame. On the contrary, the uni-directional laminates, i.e. $[90_{13}]_s$, $[45_{13}]_s$ and $[-45_{13}]_s$, are bad designs due to the higher failure indexes.

Keywords : wheelchair frame, stacking sequence, failure index, finite element.

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